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GRIEVING IN THE TIME OF COVID-19: STRATEGIES FOR COATING THE PAIN AND PSYCHIC SUFFERING OF THE POPULATION

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ABSTRACT:

Covid-19 originated in China, with a high transmission capacity made a rapid emergence of the pandemic. With everyone very concerned about knowing the virus and all its procedures, mental health was the one that had the least notoriety, causing many to have deficiencies in this area. The present study aims to describe the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief, discuss the psychosocial impacts of grief from Covid-19, thus, the focus is always on mental health in relation to the grief experienced. This is an integrative literature review study, in which 09 articles were analyzed, with the predominant area in the publications being Psychology. The analysis of the articles allows us to infer that there is a lack of coping strategies for pain and psychological suffering of the population in the face of grief, since few manage to reach the service having to resort to alternative methods, also having a great perception that the numbers of professionals qualified for this action are extremely low. Through this study, we hope to help more health professionals pay attention to the mistakes made previously during the pandemic and encourage a change in the quality of care provided to the grieving population, not only during a pandemic, but for all moments of suffering. mourning.

Key words: Death; Mourning; Covid-19; Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 PANDEMIC At the end of 2019, a new outbreak of pneumonia spread in the world population, caused by a virus called SARS-CoV-2, (COVID-19), what is known so far is that this virus originated in China, which forced different countries to mobilize to face the consequences of contamination on health and economy. Quarantine, the main way to contain the speed of contamination by COVID-19 and lethality, adopted in several regions of the world, promoted the isolation and confinement of a large number of people and the mobilization of a significant contingent of health professionals to coping with the crisis situation. Therefore, as described by Zwielewski et al (2020), the global dimension reached by COVID-19 made the World Health Organization (WHO) recognize its transmission as a pandemic. In Brazil, until September 30, 2021, 21,399,546 cases of Covid19 were confirmed, of these 20,404,701 cases are described as recovered, 398,723 cases in recovery, and 596,122 confirmed deaths, thus pointing to an incidence rate of the disease of approximately 10183, 1 per 100,000 inhabitants in Brazil, which can be viewed on the interactive COVID-19 Panel, updated monthly by the Ministry of Health (BRASIL, 2021). The main characteristic of the pandemic caused by the new coronavirus is the high transmissibility of the virus and the lethality rate varies according to the age group and clinical conditions of the patient (GRINCENKOV, 2020). Symptoms usually manifest in a clinical picture that ranges from mild cases, in which some of them may not even manifest, to very severe cases of acute respiratory syndrome. Taking into account the symptoms of the disease, the absence of vaccines and the insufficient scientific knowledge about this new virus, the most effective way to combat the proliferation of COVID-19

and a collapse in the health system is still social isolation. According to Ferguson et al (2020), there is a significant number of cases that require hospitalization and intensive care unit care, since pharmacological interventions are still insufficient and need further studies. The studies by Brooks et al (2020) and Ferguson et al (2020), point out that in order to try to control this chain of transmission and the impacts of the pandemic on the health system, considering that the number of 6 ICU beds and equipment needed for the treatment do not meet all population demand, it is extremely necessary that social isolation measures be adopted. However, Schmidt et al (2020) consider that this need has had several social and economic impacts, in addition to psychological issues that take the concerns of the disease beyond the physical symptoms.

Among these concerns, the psychological suffering experienced by both the general population and the health professionals involved in this process stands out .

Grief during the Covid-19 pandemic according to Schmidt et al (2020), Grief is a natural process in the face of the loss of someone or the breaking of a bond. Several authors have studied the theme of mourning from different theoretical approaches. In the first psychological studies on mourning, Freud (1917), in "Mourning and Melancholy" discussed a proposal in relation to the psychic dynamics of the melancholic subject, considering the perspective of the implications of object loss and of non-elaborated mourning. Freud presented mourning as a reaction to the loss of the object for which one has an investment of libidinal energy, the loss of the one one loves, culminating in behaviors that express suffering, discouragement and despondency. Unlike melancholy,

in mourning, there is the loss of a real object, and in this way, for the individual who invested energy in the lost object, the world no longer has sense or meaning that justifies the continuation with enthusiasm, these questions will be re-elaborated in a symbolic level and in the conclusion the connection of libido with another love object can occur (FREUD, 1917). Covid-19 has affected the whole world and thousands of people have died as a result of this pandemic. For the family and friends of these people, the losses are irreparable and, to deal with it, they will need a lot of support and empathy. Respect for the grieving process is one of the possible forms of care for these people, since it is a process that requires a great deal of sensitivity and subtlety, as each one can develop it in their own way, in a very unique way. This uniqueness can also be perceived in the ways in which mourning is seen, depending on the historical moment and culture of each one, since. According to Noal, Passos and Freitas (2020, p.2) “each society establishes acceptable cultural codes for the establishment of funeral rituals, which range from farewell ceremonies, tributes, to different ways of treating bodies, such as burial or cremation”. It is worth mentioning that the grieving process does not only occur when someone dies, but it can also develop due to other losses, such as, for example, the end of a relationship, the end of a cycle, the loss of a job, retirement, among others. During a pandemic, it is also common for people to suffer from what is called anticipatory grief that is expressed without the person having actually lost someone (KOVÁCS, 1992). This process is provoked in the face of uncertainties and changes in the routine of the person, who now lives isolated from their loved ones and facing the fear of losing them due to the pandemic. In this essay we specifically address the mourning of death and the

implications in this process caused by the current pandemic caused by the coronavirus that has been felt by millions of people at the same time. It is worth emphasizing that one object does not replace the space of the other, there can only be a transfer of libidinal energy from one given object to another. In this way, according to the name of the work of the aforementioned author, “Luto e Melancholia”, there is a correlation between the circumstances that appear in the title of the text, pointing out that in both there would be a profound prostration, a generalized resignation of the interest of the external world. and a considerable loss of performance (FREUD, 2017).

As already discussed in this project, Mourning is something unique. Each person reacts to loss differently. Therefore, and in agreement with Brooks et al (2020) and Xiao (2020) it is extremely important not to neglect this moment. Regarding grief in the pandemic, there are numerous psychological implications that can generate gaps and more lasting consequences in dealing with the negative consequences associated with the disease and the grieving process after death. Unfortunately, the great concern with the spread of the pandemic, the greater attention focused on the ‘cure’ or ‘eradication’ of the virus, has ignored or explored less the subject of mental health, more specifically grief. This study is based on this fact, as there are a large number of people becoming mentally ill, and the loss of loved ones significantly increases the risk of becoming ill, for this reason the group decided to talk about death, suffering, grief and the psychological impacts. We couldn’t help but talk about the professionals who are on the front lines of fighting the coronavirus, and are experiencing repeated losses, both from patients,

family members and co-workers. The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the reality and planning of people around the world. The uncertainties about the disease and the world economy affect each citizen in a particular way. The known measures to combat the transmission of the virus go through individual awareness, changes in habits and a great desire to defeat the real enemy sars-cov-2. The progressive and proportional increase in positive exams, the occupation of clinical and intensive care beds reveals the worsening, until we reach the current scenario. Fatigue invades the population and the desire to return to normal life or the new normal, the ability to respect all protocols that often seem to be exaggerated, but the solution is not individual but society. With every life lost, families and friends suffer. A team of health professionals suffers the weight of defeat and when leaving the ICU or counting the days of quarantine and there they come across people crowding in party halls, bars, amusement parks and not even using the minimum measures oriented (washing hands and wearing a mask), consume the energy of a professional who is working 24 hours on duty, but we are strong and in today's reality we are warriors and never able to give up on every human being who needs our care.

A survey carried out by the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation, comparing Brazil and Spain, shows that approximately 47.3% of essential service workers had some symptoms of anxiety and depression. More than half of them — and 27.4% of all respondents — suffer from anxiety and depression at the same time. In addition, 44.3% have abused alcoholic beverages; 42.9% suffered changes in sleep habits; and 30.9% were diagnosed with or treated for mental illness in the previous year. (UNASUS, 2020), It is worth noting that the context of Infodemia , that is, the large flow of information that spreads

quickly, has contributed to generating a large rate of misinformation. In relation to the Brazilian context, Nabuco, Oliveira, Afonso (2020) point out that in addition to Infodemia , Brazil is also experiencing the pandemic in the midst of a major political-institutional crisis. There is a structural duality, the States and the Union are in direct confrontation, disputing the model of facing the crisis, in addition to information about the real danger of the virus. There are also frequent changes in the leadership of the Ministry of Health, a federal body that should coordinate actions against the pandemic. In the midst of the dispute, the uninformed and confused population will possibly have more symptoms of anxiety, and psychosomatic problems. Based on what has been exposed, this study on grief in Covid-19 times is justified, considering that it is essential to face this reality from a broader perspective, creating specific strategies that alleviate the pain and psychic suffering of individuals.

We believe that our work is important for society and academia because talking more and more about death will break the taboos that still exist. Therefore, we want to help society and nursing students with more information as we avoid talking or thinking about death. In relation to the health team, this study is important because it returns to three important points that are impacting the mental health of this group The first refers to preventing impacts, the increase in mental health impacts related to the reduction of well-being psychosocial effects caused by the health, social and economic effects that have been affecting the entire population during the pandemic, with some population groups experiencing this more acutely. The second is about protecting people with mental illness from covid-19 and its social impacts

that can increase their vulnerability. And the third, refers to providing the necessary care to health professionals and caregivers in order to protect them too and allow them to save, protect and care for others.

Due to isolation, people cannot be with the infected patient or perform farewell rituals, actions that are part of the usual grieving process.

Public health protocols that make it impossible to visit hospitals and change traditional rituals, such as wakes and burials, impact the grieving process and the mental health of the community. In this context, the possibilities are increased for the development of a complicated grief, that is: when the grieving process takes place in a more intense and lasting way than expected, for not having been able to process the situation or say goodbye in a way that allow you to have a sense of reality and concreteness. The COVID-19 pandemic brings mental health impacts, which can involve deep loss and pain. Given this scenario, it is necessary to think about alternatives for funerals, burials and farewell rituals, it is known that farewell rituals are important for the normal grieving process of individuals and the impediment to experiencing this moment can generate intense feelings of anger, horror and shock (COGO et al. 2020) The covid-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on the daily lives of most of society, the psychic always affected by fear of contamination, mourning losses of loved ones, insecurity and lack of hope in the future... many things go through the mind without the certainty that something could improve beyond the lack of accessible professional strategies for everyone in grief. Based on what has been exposed, the following research questions are formulated: What has the scientific literature published on grief in times of a pandemic? What

psychosocial impacts of Covid-19 mourning on people's daily lives? What are the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief in the face of Covid-19?

Our general objective and specific objectives are:

To review the literature on grief experienced during the Covid-19 pandemic, and its impacts on the mental health of individuals.

- Discuss the psychosocial impacts of Covid-19 grief on people's daily lives.
- Identify the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief in the face of Covid-19.

METHODOLOGY

This study is characterized as a basic, exploratory, literature review type research that uses a qualitative approach.

According to Lakatos and Marconi (2010), basic research is the one that aims to generate new knowledge useful for the advancement of science without foreseen practical application. It involves universal truths and interests. And exploratory research provides greater familiarity with the problem in order to make it explicit or to create hypotheses.

Also, the qualitative approach is research that provides meaning and simplifies social life. In this approach, "the researcher aims to deepen the understanding of the phenomena he studies - actions of individuals, groups or organizations in their environment or social context," understanding them according to the conception of the subjects who experience the situation (GUERRA, 2014, p.3).

Therefore, this integrative literature review study sought to contemplate all these characteristics described.

The survey was carried out in a virtual environment at the Virtual Health Library (VHL), in databases considered of great relevance in the scientific environment: Latin American and Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences (LILACS), Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO) and Nursing Database (BDENF), Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System Online (MedLine), using the descriptors: “Mourning”, “Covid-19”, “Mental Health”, from the Health Sciences/Medical Subject Descriptors Headings (DeCS / MeSH), from the Virtual Health Library (VHL).

Only articles published in Portuguese, with full text available online, with a time frame between 2016 and 2021, were selected. In this sense, the filters used were full text, Portuguese language, article and year. Articles whose full texts were not available online for free and results without discussion on the topic in question were excluded.

Table 1 - Number of articles found from the database search - Rio de Janeiro - 2022.

Database	Crossing the words Control of Mourning and Covid-19 and Mental Health	Number of articles after full-text filter, language and year	Number of articles after reading
lilacs	12	7	02
Scielo	06	3	03
bdenf	05	two	02
MedLine	29	15	02
Total	52	22	09

Source : Authors themselves (2022).

For data collection, an instrument built by the authors was used, containing the following variables: journal, database, year, study location, authors’ profession, title, type of research and type of document.

Table 01 : Article Data Collection Instrument - Rio de Janeiro, 2022.

Title	periodical	Data base	Year
Mourning and non-violence in times of pandemic : precariousness, mental health and other ways of living	Psychol. social	MEDLINE	2020
That goodbye, I couldn't say": grief and suffering in times of COVID-19	sick _ Focus	LILACS	2020
The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mental health: what is the role of Primary Health Care?	Rev Bras Med Fam Community	LILACS	2020
Social and health implications that affect people bereaved by the death of family members by covid-19	Rev. sick baiana	SCIELO	2020
Effects of suppression of funeral rituals during the pandemic of COVID-19 in bereaved family members	Rev. Latin-Am. Nursing	BDENF	2020

Terminality, death and grief in the COVID-19 pandemic: emerging psychological demands and practical implications	Study psychological	MEDLINE	2020
Implications of death and mourning on the subject's mental health in the face of the pandemic	Rev. fine psych	SCIELO	2021
Experiences of grief and nursing mental health in the COVID-19 pandemic	collective health	BDEF	2021
Nurse's role in the face of grief in times of a pandemic	Electronic Magazine Health Collection	SCIELO	2021

SP	Psychology	DANZMANN, PS et al.	Research Article
RN	Nursing	Rocha, KPM et al.	Research Article
LOL	Nursing	GONÇALVES, RMV et al.	Experience Report

Source : The Authors (2022).

Finally, the analysis, evaluation, inclusion and exclusion of the works was carried out through a critical reading of the selected works to verify their authenticity, methodological quality, importance of information and representativeness. In other words, it was based on the production of the document that includes the description of the phases covered by the reviewer and the fundamental results revealed from the analysis of the articles included.

CONCLUSION

Through this study, it was possible to understand that the condition of mourning in this new pandemic scenario is a potential generator for the development of mental disorders. And that other studies are necessary, so that it is possible to know more deeply how these grieving processes are being experienced.

The analysis of the articles allows us to infer that there is a lack of strategies for coping with grief from qualified health professionals for such a situation, and that the psychosocial impacts had a great alert since there was no adequate monitoring for the population.

Finally, it is essential that there is a greater focus on changes in the face of the specific demands of this new scenario imposed by the pandemic. So that there is a change in the strategic and

Place	Profession of the Authors	authors	Document Type
RJ	Psychology/ Medicine	RENT; MAM; MARHY, EE	Original article
EC	Nursing/ Psychology/ Physical Education	OLIVEIRA, EN et al.	Original article
RJ	Medicine	NABUCO, G. et al.	Research Article
BA	Nursing	M A G A -LHÃES, JRF et al.	Original article
RJ	Psychology	OLIVEIRA-CARDOSO, EA, et al.	Original article
SP	Psychology	CREPALDI, MA et al.	Original article

psychosocial parts of the population, being a multidisciplinary work and also of a university character so that there is a greater knowledge about grief and death and is not seen only as a taboo.

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